

Performance of rice mutants in different seasons

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Samba Mahsuri, a quality rice variety grown in Andhra Pradesh, India, has a 150-d duration. Through mutation breeding, early mutants of 120-140 d duration were spotted. We evaluated 12 of them in the M5 (monsoon 1994), M6 (winter 1994-95), and M7 (monsoon 1995) generations along with their parents.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design in a 7.2-m² plot with three replications and 15- × 15-cm spacing. The low temperature in the monsoon season ranged from 22.3 to 24.4 °C during the 2 mo of seedling and vegetative growth. During the corresponding period in the winter, the low temperature was 9.2-15.5 °C, resulting in a 19 d longer flowering duration (Table 1).

Individual mutants behaved differently in the two seasons, with flowering delayed from 5.0 to 30.5 d in the winter compared with the monsoon season. Among these, M12 and M41

showed the least delay in flowering (5.0 and 11.5 d, respectively).

Grain yield in the winter was more than during the monsoon season because of the dry weather and prolonged duration. The pooled analysis of variance (data not shown) indicated that seasonal effects were significant (Table 2). Differences among the mutants and their interactions with seasons were also significant. Mutants suitable for one or both seasons were identified: M34, M41, and M47 for the monsoon season; M9, M16, and M22 for the winter; and M16 and M22 for both seasons. ■

Table 1. Mean values for days to flowering and grain yield of different rice mutants and their parent varieties.

Mutant	Days to 50% flowering					Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)				
	Monsoon		Mean	Winter		Monsoon		Mean	Winter	
	1994	1995		1994-95	Difference	1994	1995		1994-95	Difference
M7	109	112	110.5	129	18.5	4.8	5.3	5.1	5.6	0.5
M8	100	102	101.0	127	26.0	6.5	3.4	5.0	6.8	1.8
M9	91	94	92.5	123	30.5	5.1	4.7	4.9	9.1	4.2
M11	97	105	101.0	123	22.0	4.0	4.7	4.4	8.4	4.0
M12	110	106	108.0	113	5.0	4.5	4.6	4.6	2.8	-1.8
M14	107	108	107.5	125	17.5	5.3	5.1	5.2	78.4	2.2
M16	99	101	100.0	125	25.0	6.2	3.4	4.8	9.7	4.9
M22	105	108	106.5	127	20.5	5.8	5.2	5.5	11.1	5.6
M34	100	102	101.0	114	13.0	6.2	5.2	5.7	5.8	0.1
M41	105	102	103.5	115	11.5	6.9	5.3	6.1	6.6	0.5
M47	114	110	112.0	140	28.0	6.6	4.4	5.5	2.6	-2.9
Samba-Mahsuri (check)	120	122	121.0	140	19.0	4.9	5.1	5.0	7.5	2.5
Mean	105	106	105.5	125	19.5	5.6	4.7	5.2	6.9	1.8
SE±	0.4	0.3	-	0.4	-	0.2	0.3	-	0.4	-

Table 2. Mean sum of squares from pooled ANOVA.

Source	df	Days to 50% flowering	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Mutant	11	433.0** ^a	694.0**
Season	2	2444.5**	2335.0**
Mutant × season	22	29.2**	266.0**
Error	42	1.1	94.5
s ² Mutant		44.9	52.0
s ² Season		67.1	64.9
s ² Mutant × season		9.3	43.9

^a** = significant at the 0.01 level.

Using anther culture to generate fertile, doubled-haploid interspecific progeny

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Anther culture enables the rapid genetic fixation of progeny from crosses. In the context of wide crosses, anther culture can also provide fertile doubled haploid progeny with fixed introgressions that might otherwise

disappear in the course of an extended series of backcrosses. We are using anther culture and embryo rescue techniques to accelerate and improve the efficiency of the wide *O. sativa/O. glaberrima* hybridization program at WARDA. The program was expanded to classify representative japonica, indica, and *O. glaberrima* genotypes and their F₁ and F₂ progeny for suitability for anther culture.

We carried out anther cultures for 10 parental lines and the progeny of 55 japonica/japonica, japonica/indica, and *O. sativa/O. glaberrima* crosses.

Main stem boots were collected when flag leaves were exerted 4-8 cm. Panicles were disinfected and cold pre-treated at 8 °C for 10-20 d depending on varietal type. Anthers were incubated in the dark at 25±1 °C in modified N6 medium. Calli obtained were regenerated in Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium with a 16-h photoperiod at 25 °C. Plantlet regeneration was induced with the base MS salts and 3 mg thiamine-HCl L⁻¹, 1 mg IAA L⁻¹, 4 mg GA₃ L⁻¹, and 2% (w/v) sucrose.

Response to callus induction and green plantlet regeneration depended

on the genetic origin of the crosses, with japonica/*O. glaberrima* hybrids responding best, followed by pure japonica varieties and intra-japonica hybrids, japonica/indica hybrids, and pure indica and intra-indica hybrids. The least responsive were pure *O. glaberrima* and intra-*O. glaberrima* hybrids (see figure). Callus production generally peaked 4-5 wk after induction. Calli produced during this period had the greatest probability of yielding green plantlets.

We found a 5:4:1 ratio for haploids, doubled haploids, and polyploids among the regenerated plants regardless of the crosses' genetic origins (see table). The spontaneous doubled haploid lines frequently displayed partial fertility, particularly when derived from *O. sativa*/*O. glaberrima* crosses and, to a lesser extent, from japonica/indica crosses. High sterility levels might have been due to aneuploidy of the regenerated plants or fixation of sterility genes.

a. Percentage of calli induced and green and albino plantlets produced. J = japonica, I = indica, G = *O. glaberrima*. b. Percentage of calli produced over time.

More than 500 progenies of spontaneous doubled haploid fertile lines of *O. sativa*/*O. glaberrima* and 600 japonica/indica lines have been evaluated in the field to study their fertility, genetic stability, and agronomic traits. Using the seed from these trials, we are conducting specific screening trials for resistance to the major biotic and abiotic stresses in the region. ■

Ploidy levels of plants regenerated.

Background of pedigrees	Haploid lines (%)	Dihaploid lines (%)	Polyloid lines (%)
Japonica	53	40	7
Japonica and indica	50	45	5
Japonica and <i>O. glaberrima</i>	51	39	10
Mean	51	41	7.3

Response of rice anther culture to short-day treatment

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Japonica rice is widely cultivated in northern China, where the rice-growing season is only 5 mo (May to September) because of the cold climate. It takes 8-10 yr to select a pure line from a cross using conventional rice breeding and at least 4 yr using anther culture. To find ways to further reduce the time needed for rice anther culture, we conducted a study at SRRRI (35.4° N latitude).

Five parental varieties were sown on 18 Feb 1994 and transplanted on 21 Apr. When the seedlings had 7-8 leaves, they were exposed to 9 h of sunshine and 15 h of darkness for 25 d. Before the treatment, 150 ppm multi-effects triazole (MET) was applied to seedlings to

control excessive growth. Crosses were made on 4 Jun, and seeds from five F_1 plants were harvested on 28 Jun. They were sown in pots outside on 2 Jul. The panicles of the five F_1 plants were large enough for sampling on 20 Sep, at which time the micro-spores were in the early- to mid-uninucleate stage.

The same crosses were made in 1993 as checks. They were sown in 1994 on 1 May, and their panicles were sampled on 15 Aug.

Anther calli were induced on N6 medium with 2 mg 2,4-D L^{-1} , 60 g sucrose L^{-1} , 8 g agar L^{-1} , and pH 5.85. The plant regeneration medium was Murashige and Skoog (MS) with 2 mg 6-BAL L^{-1} , 0.5 mg NAAL L^{-1} , 30 g sucrose L^{-1} , 8 g agar L^{-1} , and pH 5.85.

Japonicas in northern China generally head from 15 to 25 Aug and have medium photoperiod sensitivity and medium temperature response. By combining early seeding and short-day treatment in the greenhouse, the five

parents headed from 1 to 5 Jun—nearly 80 d earlier than the same varieties grown in the ricefield under normal cultivation practices (Table 1).

When the panicles of the five F_1 crosses were ready for sampling on 20 Sep, the average day temperature was 19°C, 6°C below that of 15 Aug (the regular sampling date). The anther callus induction and green plantlet regeneration of the five F_1 crosses and their controls were then compared to check the effect of low temperature on anther culture ability. No large differences were found among the five F_1

Table 1. Heading date of five parents. Shandong, China. 1994.

Variety	Short-day treatment	Regular culture
Akenohoshi	4 Jun	23 Aug
89-7013	3 Jun	25 Aug
Xiangqueno	1 Jun	21 Aug
Kinuhikari	31 May	20 Aug
Yakomagokari	1 Jun	16 Aug